

Heterocyclic Azo Dyes as the Chromogenic Reagents for the Extraction-Photometric Determination of Silver(I)

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Silver(I) interacts with 1-(2-quinolyazo)-2-acenaphthyleneol (QAAC) and 1-(2-lepidylazo)-2-acenaphthyleneol (LAAC) to give red coloured (1:1) water-insoluble complexes at moderately alkaline pH's. The complexes are extractable in various water-immiscible organic solvents and exhibit maximum absorbance at 540-45 nm. The Sandell's sensitivity of the colour reaction is $0.0052 \mu\text{g Ag/cm}^2$ ($\epsilon = 2.08 \times 10^4$) for silver-QAAC complex and $0.0037 \mu\text{g Ag/cm}^2$ ($\epsilon = 2.88 \times 10^4$) for silver-LAAC complex. The reagents have been found to be fairly selective for the determination of silver(I) in presence of various interfering base metals.

A few reagents are known for the spectrophotometric determination of silver ions. The extractive dithione method, and the rhodamine method, are of particular importance^{1,2}. A little information has been given about a few heterocyclic azo dyes³. A method of determination of silver with PAR⁴ has been reported. 1-(2-Quinolyazo)-2-acenaphthyleneol (QAAC) has already been used for the spectrophotometric determination of various metal ions⁵⁻⁷. In the present communication, the use of QAAC and another azo dye, 1-(2-lepidylazo)-2-acenaphthyleneol (LAAC) has been explored for the spectrophotometric determination of silver.

Experimental

Reagents: A stock solution of silver (I) was prepared by dissolving appropriate amount of silver nitrate (reagent grade) in double distilled water. QAAC was synthesized⁸ and its stock solution was prepared by dissolving appropriate amount (0.323 g/l for $10^{-3}M$) in pure methanol. LAAC was synthesized by coupling 1, 2-acenaphthaquinone with 2-hydrazinolepidine (obtained by refluxing 2-chlorolepidine⁹ with hydrazine hydrate) in methanolic medium. Purity of the reagent was checked by t.l.c. and its stock solution was prepared in pure methanol (0.337 g/l for $10^{-3}M$). A few drops of pure chloroform can be added, if necessary, to the reagents before dissolving them in methanol, as these are highly soluble in chloroform. In no case reagent solutions older than four days were used.

Dilute solutions of hydrochloric acid, sodium acetate and sodium hydroxide were used for pH adjustments.

Phosphate-sodium hydroxide buffer was used for adjustment of pH around 10.0.

Apparatus: A Unicam SP-600 spectrophotometer with 10 mm matched glass cells was used for absorbance purposes.

A Beckman pH meter model Expandomatic SS-2, with a saturated calomel and glass electrode assembly was used for pH measurements.

Recommended Procedure: To a suitable aliquot containing 11 to 40 μg of silver(I), add sufficient excess of QAAC solution or to a suitable aliquot containing 12 to 37 μg of silver (I), add sufficient excess of LAAC solution, followed by 2.0 ml of phosphate/hydroxide buffer (pH ~ 10.0). Raise the volume to 10 ml keeping 50% (v/v) methanol—aqueous medium. Keep for two minutes and extract in 10 ml of freshly distilled chloroform. Measure the absorbance at λ_{max} (540-45 nm) against a reagent blank prepared under identical conditions. The amount of silver can be deduced from the calibration curve drawn under similar conditions.

Results and Discussion

Addition of methanolic solution of reagent (QAAC or LAAC) to a very dilute aqueous solution of silver(I) resulted a water-insoluble red precipitate in moderately alkaline medium, which was soluble when methanolic concentration was kept more than 75% (v/v). The precipitate was extractable in various water-immiscible organic solvents, however, chloroform or carbon tetrachloride was used for extraction purposes, as the absorbance was maximum in these and the complexes were stable at least 4 hrs.

Spectral characteristics of the complexes:

A series of solutions containing silver(I) ($2 \times 10^{-5}M$) and the reagent QAAC or LAAC ($2 \times 10^{-4}M$) at

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different pH were prepared keeping 50%(v/v) methanolic concentration and extracted in 10 ml of freshly distilled chloroform. Their spectra were recorded against a reagent blank. At all pH levels both the complexes had maximum absorbance at 540- 5 nm.

Effect of pH :

The complexes exhibited constant and maximum absorbance in the pH range 8.5–10.7 when QAAC was used and 9.0–10.1 when LAAC was used. A phosphate/hydroxide buffer of appropriate pH (~10.0) was used during further studies.

Effect of Reagent Concentration :

Absorbance data recorded for a series of solutions containing silver(I) ($2 \times 10^{-6} M$) and varying amounts of reagent (at pH~10.0) showed that 30 molar times of QAAC or 20 molar times of LAAC are required for full colour development of the complexes.

Other Physico-Chemical Characteristics :

Validity of Beer's law and optimum range for accurate determination of metal ions at a pH of 9.5 ± 0.5 , determined by Ringbom plots, are 0–4.2 ppm and 1.1–4.0 ppm respectively for silver-QAAC complex and 0–4.6 ppm and 1.2–3.7 ppm respectively for silver-LAAC complex. The Sandell's sensitivity of the colour reactions calculated from Beer's law plots comes out to be $0.0052 \mu\text{g Ag/cm}^2$ ($\epsilon = 2.08 \times 10^4 \text{ l.mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) for silver-QAAC and $0.0037 \mu\text{g Ag/cm}^2$ ($\epsilon = 2.88 \times 10^4 \text{ l.mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) for silver-LAAC complex at their λ_{max} .

Composition of the Complexes :

Composition of the complexes was determined by making use of Job's method of continuous variation. Results obtained showed that the metal ion and reagent interact in 1:1 ratio in both the cases.

Absorbance Deviations :

Measured under the experimental conditions, the mean absorbance of eight solutions containing 1 ml of $2 \times 10^{-4} M$ silver was found to be 0.415, with a standard deviation of 0.005 for silver-QAAC complex and the mean absorbance was 0.576 with a standard deviation of 0.043 for silver-LAAC complex.

Effect of Diverse Ions :

The effect of diverse ions was studied, taking 2.16 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of silver(I), adding different amounts of diverse ions and determining the amounts of silver content following the recommended procedure. It was found that lanthanides (15-fold each), In(III), Mn(II), Fe(II) and (III), Au(III), platinum metals in cold except Pd(II) (5 fold each) did not interfere. However, I^- , CNS^- , CN^- , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$, thiourea, Zn(II) interfere seriously. The amounts of other ions (in ppm), which did not cause deviation of more than $\pm 3\%$ in absorbance are given below :

PO_4^{3-} , BO_3^{3-} (1000) ; oxalate, citrate, tartrate (500) ; F^- , Cl^- , NO_2^- , SO_4^{2-} (200), Br^- , SO_3^{2-} (100) ; Cd(II), Hg(II), Cu(II) Co(II), Ni(II) (5, masked with oxalate or citrate). Pd(II) (4, masked with nitrite).

Conclusion :

Dithizone and dimethylaminobenzylidenerhodanine have been shown to be the most useful reagents for silver^{1,2}, but neither of them is specific. Silver is determined with dithizone by the monocolour, mixed colour and extractive titration methods. In case of rhodanine method, the absorbance of the complex formed, depends on the acidity of the solution, the concentration of rhodanine and time. The optimum acidity corresponds to 0.05M HNO_3 and at the optimum rhodanine concentration (0.001–0.002%), maximum absorbance is obtained in 5 min ; the colour fades after this. The temperature is also kept constant since large variations affect the colour intensity. In

TABLE I—SENSITIVITIES OF SOME METHODS FOR DETERMINATION OF SILVER

Reagents	Sensitivity ($\mu\text{g Ag/cm}^2$ for $\log I_0/I=0.001$)	Reference
Dithizone (mixed colour)	0.01 (yellow filter)	1
<i>p</i> -Dimethylaminobenzylidenerhodanine (direct)	0.005/495 nm	1
<i>p</i> -Dimethylaminobenzylidenerhodanine (indirect)	0.0026/460 nm	1
Bromopyrogallol red	0.0034/590 nm	10
Methyl phenyldimercaptothiopyrone	0.014/510 nm	11
Thiodibenzoylmethane (C_6H_6)	0.01/420 nm	12
4-(2-Pyridylazo) resorcinol	0.0054/510 nm	4
1-(2-Quinolylazo)-2-acenaphthyleneol (QAAC)	0.0052/540 nm	present method
1-(2-Lepidylazo)-2-acenaphthyleneol (LAAC)	0.0037/540 nm	..

practical analysis, the separation of silver from the other metals is required before applying either of the method mentioned above. Gold and palladium react with both the reagents and cause interference. Small amounts of mercury(II) can be tolerated in direct rhodanine method but not in the dithizone method. Dagnall and West¹⁰ recommended pyrogallol red and bromopyrogallol red methods, in which the cationic complex of silver with 1,10-phenanthroline reacts with the reagents to yield an ion-association complex. Among the heterocyclic azo dyes, only the colour reactions with PAN, *p*-PAN and 7-(2-pyridylazo)-8-quinolinol have been reported³, but details are lacking. However, PAR⁴ has been shown to be a sensitive reagent for silver. The present methods are direct and rapid. The complexes formed are fairly stable at least for 4 hrs and the colour intensity is not affected by heat. The reagents have been found to be sensitive as well as selective as many of the interfering cations could be masked with complexing anions like oxalate and citrate. The sensitivities of the colour reactions are compared with some other well known reagents reported for silver in Table 1.

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